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Mission-framed Project-based Learning and Teaching Integrating an Electric Powertrain into a Motor Glider

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ABSTRACT

Technische Hochschule Ingolstadt (THI) started in 2015 implementing mission-framed project-based learning (PBL). Instead of getting a task, which can be completely finished in a typical one-semester period, the students are working on a small part of a complex and interdisciplinary system. More genuine to professional life, they are required to meet a strict time-frame with expected results. Such mission-framed projects create an industrial working environment for project modules to deepen practice-oriented technical knowledge.

As case study, THI initiated the cross-faculty project E-Falke (e-falcon). Goal of this project is the substitution of the internal combustion engine of a glider airplane with an electric motor. Over 130 students were involved in this project, reaching for the fulfilment of pre-defined goals, such as the feasibility evaluation of the project, ground bench testing, integration of the system into the airframe and the official flight certification from the German Federal Aviation Office.

Like in conventional projects, students learned the handling of technical tasks in teams and developed their personal competences. The extensive technical

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complexity of the airplane required practical knowledge and thorough documentation for ensuing groups. This challenged the students and highlighted the need for intensive supervision and technical support during the semester projects.

This paper outlines diverse goals of all stakeholders (teachers, university, external partners) and advantages and disadvantages experienced during the implementation of this mission-framed teaching method. The lessons learnt through the years with planned optimizations for the ongoing project are presented to allow other educators to improve PBL.

1 INTRODUCTION

Universities of Applied Sciences focus on practical approaches to learning. They aim to provide to future professionals the necessary soft skills, technical and theoretical knowledge for their career. The need for educating students closer to real-world situations is lately more often expressed, when discussing the necessary skills of future employees [1-5]. The importance of learning by doing under real circumstances, initiated by Dewey more than 100 years ago, is still considered up-to-date while underlying in the term of project-based learning (PBL) [6, 7]. PBL distinguishes itself in the current teaching practice, as it is capable of reducing the gap between university and industry and meeting the demands of the growing job market. The concept of a project represent an engineer's working procedure in daily working life [8, 9].

The THI as a University of Applied Sciences consequently aims for practical orientation. Thus the university offers practical placements and projects to the students as well as collaborates with regional companies. PBL occurs multiple times in THI study programs: First, in short-term as part of seminars or in long-term as full semester-projects. To gain knowledge and competences, students are offered to work and investigate a problem, an idea, or a question inside classrooms / laboratories or outside in the field [7, 10].

After introducing the E-Falke as an example for a long-term project, this paper presents the advantages and disadvantages both for the students and the educators comparing this mission-framed project to traditional one-semester projects. These are described as arose through the implementation of this project to allow other educators to improve their implementations of PBL.

2 E-FALKE PROJECT: A CASE STUDY

2.1 Description of the project

In 2015, THI launched E-Falke as a cross-faculty project to enable additional projects modules. Technical aim of this project is to substitute the internal combustion engine of a glider airplane with electric traction and receive official flight certification from the German Federal Aviation Office. Since THI purchased the airplane (shown in Fig.1) in 2015, the work progress began.

Fig. 1. E-Falke

The primary didactic aim of this project is to create a genuine industrial working environment for project modules to deepen practice-oriented technical knowledge. E-Falke (e-falcon) came to enhance the functions of PBL with a wider range among different faculties and a challenging purpose. Students of the electrical engineering and computer science faculty as well as students of the mechanical engineering faculty and the business school participated in this project. The individual tasks were chosen according to their field of studies. By getting a common aim, these different groups of students teamed up to reach the defined requirements for flight certification. More in particular, the feasibility evaluation of the project, the ground bench testing, the integration of the propulsion and battery system into the airframe and preparing the necessary documents for the official flight certification of the German Federal Aviation Office were some of the cross-faculty goals.

Until now, E-Falke offered mission-framed student projects to most of the bachelor and master programs in the faculty of electrical engineering and computer sciences. Under the general topics of: electrical engineering and information technology, electrical engineering and electric mobility, aircraft and vehicle informatics and user experience design, students worked on concepts around Human Machine Interface, Battery Pack, Battery Management System, Electrical Interface to legacy components. In the faculty of mechanical engineering, four bachelor programs derived project: mechanical engineering, aerospace engineering, energy systems and renewable energies. Students of this faculty engaged particularly in following topics: Construction and Design of the cowling and the construction of an electrical motor and battery mount. Additionally to these marked one-semester group projects, students of all three faculties worked individually on research topics related to E-Falke-tasks as part of their bachelor or master thesis.

By far the most challenging part of the modifications is to install a redundant electrical energy storage into the plane. Certain special limitations as mechanical integration, weight, safety and budget were to consider. Student groups were working on the concept and simulation model of the energy storage. For example, one task was to determine if a low-voltage system is efficient enough to allow the minimal required performance for the certification of the plane. Here, the project demonstrates a very realistic situation for system engineers: while high-voltage systems are more efficient, the effort to install them in safe manner is higher compared to low-voltage systems. Several following groups were working on building

and testing the energy storage systems, which needed to be compatible with the rest of the purchased electric components of the traction system.

Another example of interdisciplinary teamwork was a joint project of aerospace informatics and user experience design students: without a mission-framed project both would finish their projects individually. In the frame of E-Falke both worked together to solve the problem and create the pilot interface. Pilots are used to operating combustion engines that allows maximum power at all times, e.g., to abort a landing and initiate a go-around. With battery powered drivetrains the provided maximum power depends on the state of charge of the battery systems, thus it was necessary to a) develop a user interface explaining this behaviour intuitive to the pilot and b) make the necessary algorithms working to feed the user interface with data.

2.2 Stakeholders

Apart from to the students view, several perspectives need to be considered. Such is the university management of THI that supported the project from the beginning. Numerous educators (professors, research associates, lecturers) and external industry partners have been involved in this mission.

Fig. 2. Stakeholders

2.3 Goals

As stakeholders' role and impact differs, their goals vary. Like in every project, continuous collaboration needed to be organized (Fig. 2).

- The mission-framed project style enhanced realistic environments for the project modules that were offered to students, which was (and remains) the common goal of all stakeholders. Real requirements and a clear purpose (official flight certification of the German Federal Aviation Office) ensure authenticity of student projects and increase the practical learning inside the university.

- The perspective of the university management included public relations regarding the university (in particular the aviation study programs) inside Germany and internationally. The management additionally intends an increase in aviation-related activities through supporting this mission-framed project.
- The university aims for interdisciplinary collaboration between the different faculties. This collaboration allows for knowledge gains during the practical research in order to evolve the area of E-mobility and E-flying.
- Another desired outcome from this project is to implement the E-Falke aircraft as a platform / working area, where further research and projects could be integrated. On behalf of the university, an environment with numerous potentials for future projects will be available, with which students are already familiar with. The possibility of a student group that will be capable of controlling, planning and promoting the future of E-Falke is an underlying goal.
- The external industry partners aim for the recruitment of future employees. They use the E-Falke project as a platform to promote their working facilities directly to students and get to know their potential employees in a professional working environment are substantial advantages.

3 LESSONS LEARNT

The methodology used in this research to enlighten the lessons learnt is qualitative and empirical. The stakeholders, excluding the students, observed simultaneously to their participation the interaction inside this mission-framed project. Through interviews, data about the experiences of the stakeholders with this mission-framed project were collected and are presented as follows:

3.1 Advantages

Several positive effects have been noticed since the beginning of E-Falke:

1. Students, who participated in the mission-framed project, come with higher motivation, not only because of their interest for the technical topic, but moreover because of the realistic job-related situation they experienced. For typical projects, the university teacher usually selects achievable tasks for the single student group that can be completely finished in a one-semester period. In this mission-framed project, students of different programs, fields, and faculties are working to achieve the overall goal of the project. Thus, all student groups face realistic problems, for which they are in charge. Finding solutions, verifying these solutions, and - in case they are not suitable - continue trying to find better ones, always having in mind the responsibility for the whole project. Therefore, all aspects are more authentic when participating in E-Falke. The students need to cooperate within and outside of their group. Even more they cooperate with preceding and following groups by reading and writing reports. Actually they can easily imagine the person who reads their own reports, instead of “writing it for the teacher”.

2. Like in an industrial environment, different kinds of engineers need to cooperate for the desired outcome. Here, students from different fields and faculties work together and exchange findings and ideas. Future engineers collaborate with students of the business school. Particularly, the students of business administration and management examine the value, the possibilities for sustainability and economic growth of E-Falke. The commercial aspect is not left behind; marketing students are responsible for the promotion and advertisement of the project. They are engaged in attracting more students, in terms of a student-project or volunteer work, and promoting the project to the local and international community. The extent of the cooperation and the number of the participants highlights the necessity of documentation of every aspect in the project (e.g., working process, research, team meetings etc.). Collaboration and exchange of knowledge occurs in this cross-faculty project beyond roles and positions, over “student identity”. Students of different semesters, educators with different “position” combine their knowledge, motivation and ideas to pursue their goals. In equal terms, undergraduate students work side by side with their professors and have the opportunity to experience their professionalism outside of the “strict” classroom environment. Moreover, students doing research on specific complex topics, own an “expert” role for the whole team. These experiences benefit both students and educators in interpersonal and knowledge level.
3. The collaboration of the student groups exceed the time-limitations of a one-semester-project. The need for collaboration between the students that participate in the different project modules exists not only for the student projects that are being simultaneously executed in one semester but also through the semesters. In addition, this increases the necessity of documentation and the possibility for students to stay engaged. This mission-framed project affords continuity, so that students that want to, can participate in more than one semester. There have been students that took part in E-Falke through the project module in their bachelor’s degree, concluded their bachelor thesis regarding E-Falke and registered for a project module again in E-Falke in their master’s degree. This setting offers the ability of development within familiar and interesting topics.
4. Another advantage for the student groups that were from the beginning in this mission-framed project was the freedom in the decision-making level. They were the pioneers that were responsible for planning the working progress and the further evolution of the project. No obligations, other than these of the German Federal Aviation Office for the official flight certification, were restricting the students. These obligations match to their assignment and fulfill their university credits by writing reports that will be used for official certification. Hence the assignments are kind of a duty for the achievement of the mission for the students and not a must-to-do paper they are obligated to write.

3.2 Disadvantages

The above-mentioned advantages came with some difficulties and complications that will be presented as experienced by the different stakeholders of the project.

1. More than 130 students have been involved in this long-lasting project since 2015. The guarantee of continuity requires that future participants need to be informed about the actual state of the project. Also the inquired knowledge needs to be maintained and forwarded to future students. As the project modules duration in a study program is only one semester, usually no overlap of groups in duty is given. Thus, except for the verbal transmission via the teachers, this information transfer needs to be done fully by documentation. This was a triggering point in the beginning, as some results were not precisely described. The expertise and the reason for specific decisions and steps during the developing process were vaguely illustrated. This increased the required training-time and support for the newcomers by the supervisor. Consequently, the role of every supervisor, lecturer and stakeholder that introduces the project to the students or explains a misunderstanding becomes more important. The “mediator”, the person that stands in the very beginning and through the whole project between the students and the project affects their knowledge, their interest and passion for the project. The human factor cannot be completely predicted. Inevitable changes of the teaching personnel caused deficits in the knowledge base of the project. Research assistants and lecturers have a relative short academic life. Their inquired knowledge had also to be conveyed or thoroughly documented by their absence.
2. Another inevitable consequence that appeared with the progress of E-Falke was the rising difficulty on the knowledge level. The realistic situation of this mission-framed project demands higher knowledge and skills as the project progresses. In traditional short-term projects, the demands can be relatively adjusted to the students’ background knowledge by choosing the topic of the project. The conditions of this mission-framed project create rapid evolution of the required background knowledge, which undergraduate students are lacking. Therefore, more time on training and informing the students about the subject was necessary to be dedicated at the beginning of every student project. In cases where a student group was not able to achieve its tasks in the expected timeline, somebody else had to continue their work. In a mission-framed project, the unfinished tasks remain important and become another person’s or group’s responsibility.
3. Last barrier for the teachers of the student-projects was that international students could not be involved entirely into all mission-framed tasks. The final documentation needed for the official flight certification of the German Federal Aviation Office had to be formulated in German. The international students could execute and prepare the required documents, but their documents needed translation prior to submission. This downgraded their work and minimised the authenticity of the process.

The underlying goal of the university to build an independent student-group, where a student-club would be in charge of this mission-framed project and will be organizing the research and working progress, is not achieved thus far. The commitment of the students ended by submitting their essays for getting the ECTS. Although, self-

motivated and enthusiastic about E-Falke, none took the initiative to organize a team. On the other hand most of the students who participated in the bachelor programs, later in master choose the E-Falke projects again. The reasons from the students' perspective explaining this have been only verbally researched so far. As great interest relies on this, the stakeholders of E-Falke seek to gain insights through future surveys among the students.

4 CURRENT STATE AND FUTURE WORK

This paper addressed the gains of applying PBL in higher education and the problems through this process. THI evolved this method through the years to minimise the disadvantages and keep the gain as high as possible for all participants.

Regarding rising difficulty and remaining unfinished tasks, students of master project groups were able to undertake the remaining tasks as they had the required knowledge. In comparison to lower semester bachelor students, they can execute demanding tasks and convey the required knowledge and skills to younger students. By starting such projects as bachelor modules and continue when this effect applies with master groups can this mission-framed project overcome this obstacle to a certain extent.

The answer to the need of the students for further support and guidance came outside of the university. Three retired engineers with long and valuable experience in the aerospace industry were included as support to the student groups and serve the role of an external advisor for the student projects since 2017. Additionally to their support for the students during the manufacturing phase, they sporadically attend the assessment-presentations during the semester and provide the students with useful feedback on their content and presentation skills. The fact that they are timely flexible smoothed their entry into this mission-framed project and enhanced the positive feedback from the students.

The complete substitution of the combustion engine of the powered glider airplane with electric traction and the official flight certification of the German Federal Aviation Office are ongoing processes thus far. Even though we faced problems, implementing a mission framed PBL we succeeded in bringing students closer to future working conditions and supplying them with knowledge and most importantly with a repertoire of competences. In order to develop the approach of mission-framed PBL we will evaluate the opinions and experiences of the students that participated in this project through the years. Our wish is to find ways to overcome the experienced challenges engaging the students.

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